

Anthropoides paradiseus

Blue Crane

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Group: Bird

Size: 1 - 1.2 m tall,
wingspan 1.8 - 2.1 m

Distribution:

Endemic to southern Africa, with the main range in South Africa's grasslands and Karoo, a small population in Etosha National Park (Namibia), and sporadic sightings in Botswana.

Importance:

The Blue Crane, South Africa's national bird, is an important part of the country's rich avian diversity and holds cultural significance. Although the species has adapted to human-altered landscapes such as urban areas and agricultural fields, it remains vulnerable to habitat loss, poisoning, and collisions with power lines.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 66.72 Gigabases
Approximate N50: 7.32 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Flye
Genome Length: 1.22 Gigabases
BUSCO completeness score: 100.0% [Single: 98.8%, Duplicated: 1.2%]
BUSCO database: eukaryota
Assembly N50: 10 888.1 kilobases
Contig number: 2 170

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